

Hunger Amidst Plenty in India

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Abstract:

The era of globalization introduced changes in different sectors of economy leading to use of modern technology, growth of new professions and businesses and steady withdrawal of government from priority sectors widening disparities and income inequalities in society. India, one amongst the most developing economies, has its own share of problems and vicissitudes. India, home to more than 1.39 billion people is one of the top food-producing nations in the world. The production of food grains has been increasing continuously from the 'Green Revolution' of the 1960s, and today India is one of the leading producers of rice, wheat, pulses and cotton. India is ranked first in the production of milk, and second in production of fruits and vegetables. However, the lack of storage facilities, logistics support, cold storages and closer markets or mandis means almost 30-40 % wastage of produce which could have been used to feed hungry millions. India is facing an impending humanitarian crisis on account of widespread hunger and malnutrition among its population. The poor, underprivileged and marginalized sections of society are worst affected by poverty, hunger and malnutrition. This is discernible by the continuous downslide on the Global Hunger Index (GHI). India ranked 107th out of 121 countries in 2022. With a score of 29.1, India lags behind its neighbours Sri Lanka (64), Nepal (81), Bangladesh (84) and Pakistan (99) in addressing hunger. The lack of clarity in planning, inefficiency in administration and widespread corruption are responsible for ever increasing hunger and malnutrition in India. The paper reviews actual condition of food security, policies and programs of government and reasons for persistence of large-scale hunger and malnutrition and the issue of right to food.

Keywords: Food security, Hunger, Poverty, Malnutrition, Unemployment

Introduction:

There is increasing recognition worldwide that food and nutrition is a human right, and thus there is a legal obligation to assure that all people are adequately nourished. The articulation of food and nutrition rights

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in modern international human rights law arises in the context of the broader human right to an adequate standard of living given in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948. Article 25 (1) of the UDHR asserts that ‘everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family including food, clothing, and housing.’. The right to food, and the measures that must be taken, are laid out quite clearly in article 11 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. Paragraph 1 calls on States to “recognize the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living for himself and his family, including adequate food” ...and also recognizes “the fundamental right of everyone to be free from hunger...” In the Convention on the Rights of the Child (which came into force in 1990), two articles address the issue of nutrition. Article 24 says that "States Parties recognize the right of the child to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health. (Paragraph 1)" and shall take appropriate measures "to combat disease and malnutrition . . . through the provision of adequate nutritious foods, clean drinking water, and health care (paragraph 2c). Thus, in several other international instruments, the right to food is recognized as part of the right to an adequate standard of living, focusing especially on the need for freedom from hunger.

Objective:

The present research paper tries to examine the issue of poverty in India and consequent problem of hunger and malnutrition in light of reports of International Organisations and Constitutional obligations.

Research Methodology:

The present research article is based entirely on secondary data of books, reports of various government committees, commissions, reports of international institutions and website material.

Concerns Regarding Right to Food in India:

In 2006 the total population of India was estimated as 1027 million making it the second most populous country with 28.6 percent of the population living below the poverty line. India is classified by the Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations, as a low income, food-deficit country. With 212 million undernourished people, India has the largest number of undernourished people in the world and the highest levels of child malnutrition, higher than most countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. India has committed itself to attainment of Millennium Development

Goals (MDGs) of eradication of extreme poverty and hunger and reducing to half the proportion of people suffering from hunger by 2015. However recent reports indicate that India is lagging far behind in attainment of the goal. Even though the Indian economy is growing by more than 10 percent annually, there has been increase in hunger and food insecurity in the country.

The recent data reveals the dramatic situation of under nourishment and poverty in India. 20 percent of the Indian population is undernourished, of which 57 million children are malnourished and make up one third of the world's 146 million undernourished children. According to the recent National Family Health Survey (NFHS) conducted in 2005-06, 46 percent children below 3 years are underweight; 33 percent women and 28 percent of men have Body Mass Index (BMI) below normal; 79 percent children aged 6-35 months have anaemia, as do 56 percent of ever married women aged 15-49 years and 24 percent of similar men; 58 percent of pregnant women have anaemia. . Nearly a third of children are born underweight (30 percent), which indicates that their mothers themselves are underweight and undernourished. Malnutrition also increases during early childhood, particularly for girls, reflecting persistent gender discrimination against girl children.

In terms of calorie consumption, the picture is even worse. According to the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) survey of 2004-05, the average daily intake of calories of the rural population has dropped by 106 Kcal (4.9 percent) from 2153 Kcal to 2047 Kcal from 1993-94 to 2004-05 and by 51 Kcal (2.5 percent) from 2071 to 2020 Kcal in urban areas. The average daily intake of protein decreased from 60.2 to 57 gm in rural India between 1993-94 and 2004-05 and remained stable at around 57 gm in urban areas during the same period. From an estimated population of 1027 million people in India, 28.6 percent lives below the poverty line, of which 23.6 percent in the urban areas and 30.2 percent in the rural areas. There is strong correlation between under nourishment and poverty and discrimination. Poverty prevents persons from fully realising their potential and enjoying their rights. Poverty could be caused by denial of rights like access to land, forests, water; displacement for developmental purposes, inefficient agricultural practices or change in governmental policies leading to a slowdown in or closure of industry leading to loss of employment and income

Government Policy and Food Supply:

Hunger and malnutrition among people is also critically linked to the ability of the individual to earn a living or have access to food producing resources and feed themselves. The Government of India has adopted many food-based schemes and food assistance programmes to prevent hunger and malnutrition in

the country. With the increase in food grain production from 50 million tons in 1950-51 to around 211 million tons in 2001-2002. India runs the largest food-based schemes and food assistance programmes in the world. These programs of Sampurna Gramin Yojana, Mid-day Meal Scheme, Integrated Child Development Scheme, National Benefit Maternity Scheme for BPL pregnant women, National Old Age Pension Scheme for destitute persons of over 65 years, Annapurna Scheme, Antyodaya Anna Yojana, National Family Benefit Scheme and Public Distribution Scheme for BPL & APL families are at the forefront to provide food grains to the poor at affordable rates and prevent hunger and malnutrition.

However this increase in food production did not translate in access to food for all and decrease in food insecurity. This indicates that a large part of the population cannot afford adequate food to maintain a healthy and sustainable life. The increased in food grain production in India in the last fifty years has assured food grain availability in the country. Also, India has been able to maintain a high level of food grain reserves for past decade. Food grains were available but the poor did not have the money to purchase them. This meant that even the subsidised food grains were not purchased from the Public Distribution System (PDS) due to lack of money. Having no access to affordable food makes people eat less and over the years become malnourished, children, women, the old and infirmed are more susceptible to ill-health due to lack of food.

Supreme Court and Right to Food:

In India, under the Indian Constitution, there is no fundamental right to food but the fulcrum of justifiability of the right to food comes from a much broader “right to life and liberty” as enshrined in Article 21. The Directive Principles of State Policy of the Indian constitution under Article 47 states, the state shall regard the raising of the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and improvement of public health as among its primary duties. Generally, the right to food also implies three types of duty or obligation—obligation to protect, respect and fulfil. The obligation to protect requires measures by the state to ensure that enterprises or individual do not deprive individual of their access to adequate food for life. The obligation to respect existing access to adequate food requires states parties not to take any such measure that results in preventing access to adequate food for human existence. The obligation to fulfilment, to strengthen people’s access to and utilization of resources means to ensure their livelihood, including food security and right to livelihood is included under right to life in Indian Constitution.

Food grains Production in India and Supply:

The food production in India prior to the Green Revolution was dismal and India had to depend on imports for meeting the demand of the people. However, after green revolution the scenario changed and today India is producing a large amount of food grains in excess of actual demand in the country. The excess amount of food grains has helped in strengthening the buffer stock in the country. In addition to the requirements of wheat and rice under the Targeted Public Distribution Scheme, the Central Pool is required to have sufficient stocks of these in order to meet any emergencies like drought/failures of crops, as well as to enable open market intervention in case of price rise. The central pool requires maximum (269 lakh tons or 26.9 million tonnes) of rice and wheat on 1st July every year. But, the procurement policy of the government has amassed a huge amount of buffer stock which is lying unutilised in godowns and there is problem of their safe storage. There is greater danger of this buffer stock getting damaged due to rodents and climatic variations like rainfall, extreme cold and hot-humid conditions.

However, the increased in foodgrain production and amount of foodgrain available in the central pool has not translated into food grains reaching the poor and needy. In fact, there are more hungry people in the country than 1960s, even after the buffer stock is overflowing with food grains. The average daily intake of the poorest section of the society is has become a matter of concern. The daily per capita net availability of foodgrain has been falling steadily and dangerously during the “reform” years. If we take five-year averages for those years from 1992 to 2010 — the figure declined every five years without exception (see table). From 474.9 grams of cereals and pulses for the years of 1992-96 to 440.4 grams for the period 2007-2010 (The 2011 figure is yet to come). A fall of 7.3 per cent. There has not been a single five-year period that saw an upward blip. If we consider the average of latest five years, it was 440.4 grams for the period 2006-10. That's lower than the corresponding period half a century ago. It was 446.9 for the years 1956-60. If production is rising and per capita availability is declining, it means that the foodgrain is not available to those who most need it. It also implies that the gap between those eating more and those eating less is worsening. And that food prices and incomes of the poor are less and less in sync with each other. This might be one among several reasons why malnutrition rates for children under-five in India are double than those in Sub-Saharan countries.

Conclusion:

To overcome food insecurity and fight against hunger and malnutrition India has formulated several policies. However, these policies are not sufficient to address the hunger situation in the countries and there

exists a gap between the policies of ending hunger and their implementation. Lack of effective implementation, corruption, inefficiency and discrimination deprive the poor in India who continuously struggle for survival and endure different degrees of chronic and endemic hunger. Several assessments show that the bulk of the government funding does not reach the rural areas or to the urban poor directly due to various leakages in the distribution process. The social welfare schemes are poorly implemented, central provisions of funds are inadequate or underutilised and are not even demanded by the states, food grains meant for the poor are diverted and enjoyed by powerful elites, discrimination in distribution, irregular and untimely supports, corruption, biased political influences at grassroots are elements of a complex web of causes contributing to widespread hunger in a society of plenty. With Liberalisation of the economy, several changes in different sectors have adversely impacted food security of the people. The failure of the government to protect the people and facilitate their adaptation to changing realities has accentuated the crisis of hunger and consequent malnourishment in the country. The provision and protection of people concerning access to productive resources, water, employment and wages and proper implementation of social security programs will in the long run guarantee success against poverty, hunger and malnourishment in the country.

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